

Digital Inclusion through Fabrication Technologies, Universidad Estatal a Distancia

Inclusión Digital por medio de tecnologías de fabricación, Universidad Estatal a Distancia

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Abstract

The social goal of state universities unequivocally involves social inclusion. Hence, one of its fundamental elements should be digital inclusion, since it enhances social inclusion by helping close the digital divide. Some authors point out different elements that make it possible to ensure, or at least come close to, digital inclusion. This paper does an in-depth analysis of ten initiatives proposed by Universidad Estatal a Distancia, closely associated with digital fabrication technologies that pursue this goal. These proposals are detailed and analyzed in the light of some concepts and their contribution to digital inclusion is measured qualitatively. This paper lists the virtual platforms where information can be found to replicate some of these initiatives in order to allow anyone interested to learn a little more about them, plan some strategy to replicate the experience, and have a parameter with which to compare the results obtained. You are cordially invited to read and share your experience.

Keywords

Digital inclusion, digital fabrication technologies, open educational resources, democratization of knowledge

1 Introduction

Universidad Estatal a Distancia was created in Costa Rica by Law No. 6044, which reads: "ARTICLE 1: Universidad Estatal a Distancia (UNED) is created as a higher education institution specialized in teaching through social communication means" (1977, p. 1). Since its origins its main objectives have been democratizing knowledge and spreading a culture of openness to all corners of the country.

Over the years, UNED has advanced in achieving this objective by having campuses spread throughout the national territory and serving vulnerable populations, such as minorities. This is why, in recent years, digital inclusion has gained even more importance. With today's technological advances, the most vulnerable populations are at a greater disadvantage. But what is digital inclusion? Valeria Castro defines it as follows:

...digital inclusion can be understood as a series of practices, skills, and abilities through which the use of ICTs is sought to be enhanced to avoid limiting it to its basic uses and to provide critical capabilities that allow for an effective appropriation of technology. [...It is] a process that requires mental and cultural transformations that must occur in people to

produce real technological appropriation, which provides adequate and sufficient capabilities to survive in the information and communication society and that enhances a critical understanding of the technological era in which we find ourselves (Castro Obando, 2021, p. 22).

When the purpose of a university is to democratize knowledge and bring a culture of openness to the length and breadth of the country, this concept is here to stay. Evidently, it is essential to determine how to achieve the aforementioned inclusion, to do so, Castro Obando (2021, p.22) provides some insights that allow reviewing a university's work by considering the three areas of action or dimensions of digital inclusion: "access to ICT (equipment and development of telecommunications infrastructure), digital literacy, and digital appropriation (use of ICTs and reinvention and adaptation of their uses)" (Castro Obando, 2021, p. 22).

In other words, there are three dimensions to be considered in the work for digital inclusion. This, in turn, is also reinforced by the need to contribute to the UN 2030 Agenda and its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (Naciones Unidas, n. d.).

Although it cannot be overlooked that there are political issues to be considered, Sebastián Benítez points out possible measures of action to guide this task (Benítez Larghi, 2020, p. 150; Benítez Larghi, 2023, p. 33):

- Guarantee the supply of quality Internet connection throughout the neighborhood, i.e., guarantee universal access.
- Promote a dialogue and exchange of different points of view regarding the expectations and fears about ICTs among the different stakeholders of the educational communities.
- Promote a critical view on the part of managers, teachers and students to allow them to transcend commercial impositions and the language of brands.
- Propose and design alternative communication platforms and, at the same time, critically challenge the corporate logic of social media.
- Guarantee families access to educational sites at no cost (without data consumption).
- Promote access to devices considering those practices that make them socially meaningful within the beneficiaries' social context.
- Design digital literacy programs that consider the beneficiaries' daily needs and respond to a logic of constant training in informal spaces (i.e. through training programs registered territorially and managed by the community stakeholders themselves).
- Have the State and its agencies produce and disseminate different video tutorials that, in simple language, aim at solving the most frequent issues and obstacles for the appropriation of digital technologies and that provide practical tools for digital communication, online marketing, and electronic payment options for products and services.
- Promote and disseminate tax exemption policies, tax reliefs for entrepreneurs, and targeted benefits for the banking of microenterprises.
- Coordinate with the private sector the recognition and certification of the digital skills of young people from vulnerable neighborhoods and complement them with formal studies.

These and other guidelines developed globally and in Latin America have a national echo. The National Council of Rectors (CONARE) stated the following in its last "State of Education" report:

...it is imperative to implement the national agreement to have an interconnected society and widely promote digital literacy and citizenship, for which the following actions are necessary:

close the digital divide and the differences in access to technology and connectivity among households and regions – for which the distribution of equipment to students in their homes is imperative; and have an interconnected educational network with quality infrastructure and connectivity. (Programa Estado de la Nación, 2023, pp. 142-143).

Given that the work dimensions mentioned by Castro, the policies suggested by Benítez, and the tasks assigned by CONARE are constantly considered, UNED has put forward several actionable initiatives to reach the desired goal. This paper deals with these actions and how digital fabrication technologies are embedded in them. Furthermore, since UNED's culture of openness has also contributed to fulfill these objectives, it is also discussed in the description of each initiative.

2 Methodology

Universidad Estatal a Distancia (UNED) of Costa Rica has made efforts for the openness and democratization of knowledge since its inception. With the establishment of the Observatorio de Tecnología en Educación a Distancia and, later, with the establishment of the Kä Träre Fabrication Laboratory (Fab Lab Kä Träre), digital fabrication technologies were included in the equation. Figure 1 shows an implementation timeline of the ten initiatives discussed in this paper.

These ten initiatives include open elements, the integration of one or more technologies and, of course, the target population to whom they were directed. The documentation that supports the work carried out in each initiative has been published openly so that anyone interested in replicating them or simply learning about them can do so without the need to track down the information.

Below you will find the contribution made by the Fabrication Laboratory (Fab Lab) to each initiative, the technologies used and how they contributed to digital inclusion according to the areas proposed by Castro (2021). It is worth mentioning that some of these initiatives are still active.

2.1 Pay Phones as Wi-Fi Kiosks

Of the ten projects mentioned in this paper, this one predates the existence of UNED's Fabrication Laboratory. It is included because it was the first attempt to provide connectivity to the communities near UNED's regional campuses. For this purpose, pay phones in several community parks were used as the Wi-Fi kiosks to provide this connectivity.

Antennas were placed inside the phone booths from where the internet signal was distributed so that people could connect with their own devices. The cantons with the lowest human development index -- namely, León Cortés, Limón, Buenos Aires, Pococí, Tarrazú, Sarapiquí, Los Chiles, Matina, Talamanca, and Alajuelita -- were selected for this project.

Regarding the three areas of action indicated by Castro, this project contributed to both access and appropriation; however, digital literacy was not a strong component. This weakness was addressed by posting signs telling people that they were in an area with an internet signal and how to connect to it using their devices.

2.2 IR Remote

The same year that the UNED Fab Lab was established, an initiative to use IR Remote arose as it had the potential of impacting many people. A digital board using a Wii (video game console) controller and components that can be bought in any electronics store -- i.e., an infrared LED emitter, a switch, AA batteries with their corresponding holder, cables and little else -- were the technologies used. The use of this device was based on the work of Dr. Johnny Chung Lee, a specialist in Human-Computer Interaction at Carnegie Mello University in Pennsylvania.

Figure 1: Timelines of UNED's Initiatives in Search of Digital Inclusion

For this initiative, the welding, building, and cutting work was done at several workshops. Workshops were held in several educational centers around the capital city. As part of the strategy to spread the use of this resource, kits were made and delivered with all the components and instructions necessary to build the laser pointer needed to use a digital whiteboard.

All three dimensions of digital inclusion considered by Castro were embedded in the project: access, literacy, and appropriation. Access was evident as kits were brought to the target population; literacy was achieved not only through the workshops held in different places, but also with publications in the Observatorio de Tecnología en Educación a Distancia of UNED and tutorials on how to assemble the laser pointers. Finally, appropriation occurred through the different uses given to the digital boards. Although the current Wii controllers do not allow using them as boards, people still ask about this initiative.

2.3 Fab Lab Kä Träre

In 2014, UNED made the decision to establish a Fabrication Laboratory (Fab Lab) which was strategically assigned to the Vice Presidency of Research. The Fab Lab Kä Träre came into existence to experiment with technologies and their application to distance education. It is an open space that welcomes anyone with a desire to learn about digital fabrication technologies and those who have a project. Its creation statement declares: "We believe in open innovation and entrepreneurship to build a better future and social, economic and environmental opportunities for all people." (Red de Investigación, n. d., para 1).

Since the Fab Lab is part of the Fab Foundation, it utilizes basic digital manufacturing technologies, additive and subtractive manufacturing, electronics components, and traditional manufacturing technologies (e.g. sewing, cabinetmaking or working with lights) while implementing the Design Thinking methodology.

Regarding Castro's areas of action for digital inclusion, access is fully covered since the Fab Lab is a space open to all. Literacy is also included since training is provided to different groups. In fact, currently, a technical training program in digital manufacturing technologies is being developed for people interested in this subject matter. This program will allow participants to obtain a certification that will open job opportunities for them. As for appropriation, although it is constantly promoted, it has not necessarily been fully achieved.

2.4 Mini Fab Lab Turrialba

The first effort to bring digital fabrication technologies to regions beyond UNED's main campus was a project called "El chunche viajero" (loosely translated as Traveling Stuff). The idea was to send packages with technological components to different sites to make them available to the student population so that they could begin experimenting with them. The idea evolved and was transformed into a specific space with its own work schedule where digital fabrication technologies would be explored in depth and used to solve community problems.

The project was carried out at the university campus in Turrialba and was overseen by two Computer Engineering students. Several groups of people from the community, ranging in ages from school children to senior citizens, took courses that lasted several weeks. Each group identified a need in their neighborhood and looked for ways to solve it.

In this case, Castro's three dimensions were addressed, since access was provided to all those interested, participants became digitally literate and appropriated the technology by building their own solutions. Thus, this project became the basis for other broader projects.

2.5 OER Node

This Open Educational Resources (OER) project -- still active -- emphasizes openness to democratize knowledge. It works hand in hand with the Fab Lab to support digital inclusion initiatives. The working

group consists of an interdisciplinary team of professionals, including graduate and research students, who study, analyze, train, and design these types of resources.

This project encompasses all of Castro's areas of action to achieve digital inclusion. Access ranges from safekeeping Open Educational Resources (OER) for different populations and internal work proposals to the open availability of all digital resources to all. Literacy includes free courses for staff and students. Moreover, a virtual course on this subject is currently being developed as well. Digital appropriation in this case involves participants' learning to recognize, search, adapt and create OER.

2.6 Arduino Kits for UNED's Students

This project marked a milestone at the University. Printed books or digital materials located on virtual platforms used to be distributed to students every quarter. But in 2017, instead of this type of materials, it was decided that technology students and those with special educational needs would receive an Arduino kit instead of a textbook. These kits contain an Arduino board with the corresponding wires, actuators, sensors, connection cables, and a testing board.

This opened a novel approach that allowed identifying the need and the possibility of replicating the project in other subject areas. For instance, Educational Informatics students today utilize kits of various types of electronic boards throughout their studies.

As to Castro's areas of digital inclusion, access is given by the University's provision of such materials; literacy is achieved through a course to introduce its use, and appropriation results from using such materials in the solution of a real need detected during their educational work.

2.7 Tablets and Raspberry Pi 3

UNED's student population is spread throughout the country, which includes very remote areas with low or no connectivity and considerable poverty. Furthermore, according to the Dirección de Asuntos Estudiantiles (DAES), a large group of students does not own any kind of technological device for their academic activities. This initiative addressed this population; one group of students was given tablets and another Raspberry Pi 3 with its components to assemble a kind of desktop computer. This project was carried out in 2018, and its details, technological components, and results are available to all at <https://ocw.uned.ac.cr/recursos/dispositivos-tecnologicos-para-el-estudiantado-uned/>.

In this case, Castro's digital access was provided by sending the devices from the headquarters to different parts of the country. Literacy was achieved through various means, even as some participants sought additional information and help on their own on how to use these devices rather than receiving digital literacy from the project. As for appropriation, it was fully achieved as participants from both groups even asked to keep the devices after the end of the pilot project.

2.8 Regional Fab Labs

This is a still active project which stemmed from the proposal mentioned in point 2.4. The experience of the Mini Fab Lab in Turrialba served as the basis for replicating it in different regions of the country. It began at two sites: Puntarenas and San Carlos.

In these facilities, a regional fabrication laboratory with two 3D printers, a laser cutter, various tools and technology kits for the development of projects was installed after assigning security and appointing a person to oversee the Regional Fab Labs.

As is evident, access was provided not only to UNED students, but also to the local communities. In terms of literacy, the people in charge of the Regional Fab Labs train those who come to work there. Appropriation has been slow; unfortunately, when someone is assigned a task, they might not be interested in it, so motivating them has been challenging.

2.9 Mobile Fab Lab

This project seeks to bring digital fabrication technologies to people who would not otherwise get to know them. It is still active and, although no specific vehicle adapted for this purpose is available today, other institutional means of transportation are used to go to the communities and bring the equipment to be used by the populations that come to the site. The technologies brought to these regions include a little bit of everything: 3D printers, computer numerical cutters, 3D scanners, board kits, and examples of projects elaborated with these technologies.

It is in this way that access to digital technologies is provided. Literacy is not the primary objective because the visits are usually short. Yet, visits are complemented with virtual courses in the evenings to serve those interested people who study or work during the day. Appropriation occurs gradually, as it depends on the technologies taken to the regions.

2.10 2RACHEL

This last project is also active and consists of the use of a device called Remote Area Community Hotspot for Education and Learning (RACHEL). This is a portable device, powered by a battery, which contains copies of websites that can be accessed through technological devices without the need for an Internet connection. With this type of device, it is possible to reach specific communities or groups having none or restricted connectivity.

The first phase of this project brought RACHEL to inmates. In Costa Rica, detention centers, whether transitory or permanent, are areas where connectivity is cut off and technological devices taken in are blocked. For this reason, UNED students who are incarcerated in these centers have very limited academic offerings and options since some subject matters require online connectivity. Thus, RACHEL has become an alternative solution for this population.

This project also makes use of Open Educational Resources and works on three dimensions: educational, technological and logistical-administrative. Guidelines to follow and areas of improvements have been determined for each of them. A second phase is expected to be carried out with populations with low or no connectivity and communities with spaces where people can gather.

Regarding the areas of action mentioned by Castro, this project achieves access by installing the RACHEL devices where required; digital literacy happens through visits where people are taught to use the devices, and appropriation is achieved when participants use the device for their academic activities. It should be pointed out that the first phase was so successful that removing the devices was difficult because participants wanted to continue using them.

3 Conclusions

As has been indicated, the ten initiatives have been geared toward different target populations and have had different specific objectives, but they all shared a common goal: to democratize knowledge. Table 1 summarizes this information and the areas of digital inclusion (Castro, 2021) that are covered by each initiative. The mathematical symbol for "approximate" (\approx) is used to indicate that the initiative had some contribution to the achievement of the dimension.

Table 1 only summarizes the 10 initiatives discussed in this paper, which were selected because of their relationship with the fabrication laboratories and the nature of the Fab24 Conference and Symposium. However, UNED also promotes other initiatives that contribute to digital inclusion and the democratization of knowledge, but they were excluded because they are beyond the scope of this paper.

Table 1: Initiatives and areas of digital inclusion (Castro, 2021) to which they contributed

Initiative	Access to ICTs	Digital Literacy	Digital Appropriation
Pay Phones as Wi-Fi Kiosks	X	≈	X
IR Remote	X	X	X
Fab Lab Kä Träre	X	X	≈
Mini Fab Lab Turrialba	X	X	X
OER Node	X	X	X
Arduino Kits for UNED's Students	X	X	X
Tablets and Raspberry Pi 3	X	≈	X
Regional Fab Lab	X	X	≈
Mobile Fab Lab	X	X	≈
RACHEL	X	X	X

In reviewing the selected initiatives and their contributions, it is evident that digital inclusion -- the first of Castro's areas (2021) -- is fully covered by the objectives and populations targeted in each case as it is an essential component of all projects.

Literacy is covered in more than 90% in this sample of projects, as in one of them -- Tablets and Raspberry Pi 3 -- students themselves sought to learn about the technology by their own means rather than UNED providing the digital literacy required. Nevertheless, it is worth remembering that these people did not have any technological devices for their work and, when they received their Raspberry Pi 3 kits, they looked for someone to help them assemble it rather than waiting for the manuals to be distributed at a later date. Still, whether on their own or provided by the project, these populations were exposed to digital literacy.

Regarding appropriation, the third and last area determined by Castro (2021), the analysis shows that it is least present. Of the three initiatives in which appropriation was not completely achieved, two did not include it as their main objective. These are the Kä Träre Fab Lab and the Mobile Fab Lab. The first is the entity from which the projects are generated, but by itself it does not cause appropriation. The second aimed at raising awareness about digital fabrication technologies and motivating people to learn and use these technologies to come up with answers to different situations or problems. The third, the Regional Fab Labs project, does have the goal of generating appropriation, but this project is still under development, so it is expected that this dimension will be emphasized in the future.

Digital fabrication technologies have contributed to the achieving UNED's objectives of democratizing knowledge and bringing a culture of openness to all regions of the country. Many of these initiatives have already been completed and have left their mark on the University as they continue to be used as a reference for new projects. Furthermore, having the information about most of these proposals open has turned them into an invaluable reference for similar experiences both within UNED and beyond.

4 References

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